

Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed on ring samples from 10 kHz to 1 MHz at room temperature

Draft A

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Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	2
2	Reference samples	3
3	Measurements to be made.....	4
	3.1 Quantity to be measured.....	4
4	Organisation.....	4
	4.1 Pilot Laboratory	4
	4.2 Participants.....	4
	4.3 Comparison schedule	5
5	Measurement instructions	5
	5.1 Measurements of the samples	5
6	Measurement results	6
	6.1 Calculation of the reference value and its uncertainty	6
	6.2 Evaluation of comparison results	7
	6.2.1 Total losses results	8
7	Summary and conclusions	11
8	References.....	11

1 Introduction

The measurement of specific total power loss in magnetic materials is enshrined within four international Standards covering three different geometries. These include Epstein frame at frequencies between 50 Hz and 400 Hz [1] and frequencies from 400 Hz to 10 kHz [2], Single Sheet Tester (SST) at power frequencies [3] and rings at frequencies from 20 Hz to 200 kHz [4]. However some soft magnetic materials, such as ferrites and nanocrystalline materials, are used in high frequency applications, where frequencies in the MHz range are regularly used. For these applications, there is no standard test method for power loss, as such the metrology and good measurement practices need to be defined to allow for better characterization and understanding of these materials as well as future standardization.

Previously comparisons promoted by EURAMET and the IEC TC 68 at lower frequencies have confirmed good reproducibility for both the Epstein and SST methods, with an uncertainty around 1% for the power loss measurement. These comparisons, however, were only focused on measurements at 50 Hz and room temperature [5] and to date no comparisons on soft magnetic materials up to 1 MHz has been carried out.

Within the HEFMAG project a new comparison was performed for specific total power loss measurements between 10 kHz and 1 MHz. For this a single experimental set-up based on IEC standard 60404-6 with a small toroid was used. Measurements were performed using a ferrite toroid and two nanocrystalline toroids with different permeability.

As an output of the comparison two documents are drafted in parallel to the measurements. These documents shall reflect the current state of knowledge:

1. Report of measurement results: This document contains the results of measurements and their accuracy for each laboratory and a discussion of the findings during the round robin comparison. This report will be shared through a report to IEC TC 68 and made available to the stakeholders.
2. A Good practice guide on the measurement of power losses in small rings up to 1 MHz at room temperature has been developed for all loss measurements, including details relevant to the high frequency ones. This document can provide a basis for discussions on CMC revisions and updates within the IEC TC 68.

2 Reference samples

The aim of this task is to evaluate and, in the future, reduce the uncertainty of power loss measurements at high frequencies up to 1 MHz at room temperature according to IEC 60404-6.

Three samples were used:

- One ring of N30 ferrite (see catalogue information in appendix A)
- Two Vitroperm rings (VAC 250F and VAC 500F) (see catalogue information in appendix B)

All samples were demagnetized prior to measurement.

3 Measurements to be made

3.1 Quantity to be measured

Measurement of specific total power loss P_s (W/kg) at specific peak magnetic polarisation J_m were performed according to the standard IEC 60404-6.

4 Organisation

4.1 Pilot Laboratory

Pilot laboratory:

INRIM
Massimo Pasquale
Strada delle cacce 91 10135
Torino Italy
E-mail: m.pasquale@inrim.it

4.2 Participants

The following participants have expressed their interest in participations in the comparison:

Acronym	Laboratory	Country	Contact
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica	Italy	Massimo Pasquale m.pasquale@inrim.it
NPL	National Physical Laboratory	United Kingdom	Stuart Harmon stuart.harmon@npl.co.uk Daniel Brunt daniel.brunt@npl.co.uk
UNOTT	University of Nottingham	United Kingdom	Gaurang Vakil Gaurang.Vakil@nottingham.ac.uk Ram Ramanathan Mathavan Jeyabalan Ram.Ramanathan@nottingham.ac.uk

4.3 *Comparison schedule*

The comparison was carried out by a circulation scheme. The organization of the comparison follows: 1. INRIM, 2. NPL, 3. UNOTT and then the samples was returned to INRIM.

It was expected that each participant covers the freight charges from his location to the next on the list. Each participant was responsible for insurance of the samples from arrival in their laboratory until arrival in the subsequent laboratory.

The transport of the travelling standards was arranged by door-to-door parcel service.

5 **Measurement instructions**

5.1 *Measurements of the samples*

Each participant performed a small set of repeated measurements using their standard equipment and measurement procedure. The specific total losses were measured stepwise from the lowest to the highest peak polarization value J_m given below at given frequencies. The measuring temperature shall be 23 ± 5 °C.

Parameters for N30 Ferrite	
Frequency (kHz)	Specific total power loss at J_m (T)
10	0.05, 0.1, 0.2
20	0.05, 0.1, 0.2
50	0.05, 0.1, 0.2
100	0.05, 0.1, 0.2
200	0.05, 0.1, 0.2
500	0.05
1000	0.05

Parameters for V250F	
Frequency (kHz)	Specific total power loss at J_m (T)
10	0.1, 0.5
20	0.1, 0.5
50	0.1, 0.5
100	0.1, 0.5
200	0.1
500	0.1
1000	0.1

Parameters for V500F

Frequency (kHz)	Specific total power loss at J_m (T)
10	0.1, 0.5
20	0.1, 0.5
50	0.1, 0.5
100	0.1, 0.5
200	0.1, 0.5
500	0.1
1000	0.1

6 Measurement results

6.1 Calculation of the reference value and its uncertainty

For all measurements of specific total power loss, the evaluation of this comparison was performed following procedure A in [6].

- the modified reduced observed chi-squared value by the formula:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{obs} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - x_{ref})^2}{u_i^2}} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of participants, x_i is the results of the total losses of the i -th participant of the comparisons and u_i is declared standard uncertainty of the i -th participant of the comparison.

- the reference value of total losses x_{ref} by the formula:

$$x_{ref} = \mathbf{u}^2(x_{ref}) \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{u_i^2} \quad (2)$$

- standard uncertainty of the reference value of total losses $u(x_{ref})$ by the formula:

$$u(x_{ref}) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{u_i^2} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

- the degree of equivalence of the measurement standard d_i by the formula (4) with a corresponding uncertainty by the formulas (5), (6):

$$d_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (4)$$

$$u(d_i) = \sqrt{u^2(x_i) + u^2(x_{ref})} \quad (5)$$

$$E_n = \frac{|d_i|}{2u(d_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where d_i is degree of equivalence and $u(d_i)$ is the standard uncertainty of the degree of equivalence.

The declared uncertainties are judged as reliable if equation $E_n < 1$ is satisfied, that is a confirmation of the relevant rows from CMC.

6.2 *Evaluation of comparison results*

Parameters of measured samples:

Material	Cross Section ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$)	Mean Magnetic Path Length ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$)	<i>N</i> turns (B coil)	<i>N</i> turns (H coil)	Density (kg/m^3)	<i>B</i> coil Cross Section ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$)
N30 ferrite	12.33	39.89	6	6	4800	12.33
Vitro 250F V165 Sample n.3	14.4	40.8	6 2	6	7200	39.7
Vitro 500F W403 Sample n. 3	14.4	40.8	6 (0.1 T) 2 (0.5 T)	6	7200	39.7

$$R_H = 9.922 \pm 0.001 \, \Omega \text{ (INRIM)}$$

$$R_H = 4.96 \pm 0.001 \, \Omega \text{ (INRIM)}$$

6.2.1 Total losses results

Table I: N30 ferrite results

Frequency (kHz)	Magnetic Polarisation (T)	INRIM		NPL		Weighted Analysis			d_i		$u(d_i)$		E_n	
		Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty (k = 1) (%)	Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty (k = 1) (%)	$\bar{X}_{weighted}$ (W/kg)	St Dev. u^2 (%)	u (%)	INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL
10	0.05	0.08315	3	0.0874	1.1	0.0869	1.067	1.033	0.003744	-0.000503	0.0027	0.0013	0.70624	0.19140
10	0.1	0.55840	1.7	0.603	1.7	0.5806	1.445	1.202	0.022244	-0.022244	0.0118	0.0124	0.94392	0.89692
10	0.2	4.36166	1.5	4.42	3.9	4.3687	1.960	1.400	0.006993	-0.047272	0.0896	0.1828	0.03904	0.12933
20	0.05	0.21381	5	0.2083	0.55	0.2083	0.299	0.547	-0.005485	0.000066	0.0108	0.0016	0.25511	0.02055
20	0.1	1.37852	3	1.406	0.50	1.4051	0.243	0.493	0.026590	-0.000739	0.0419	0.0099	0.31706	0.03741
20	0.2	10.77561	1.5	10.56	2.5	10.7190	1.654	1.286	-0.056615	0.157263	0.2124	0.2979	0.13324	0.26398
50	0.05	0.69788	3	0.722	0.65	0.7206	0.404	0.635	0.022685	-0.001065	0.0214	0.0066	0.52925	0.08124
50	0.1	4.87429	1.5	4.76	0.70	4.7842	0.402	0.634	-0.090132	0.019629	0.0792	0.0451	0.56929	0.21765
50	0.2	34.11032	1.5	35.7	1.0	35.1789	0.692	0.832	1.068582	-0.474925	0.5895	0.4613	0.90640	0.51477
100	0.05	2.12037	1.8	2.25	1.8	2.1853	1.620	1.273	0.064902	-0.064902	0.0472	0.0491	0.68714	0.66046
100	0.1	12.79745	1.8	13.88	1.8	13.3390	1.620	1.273	0.541572	-0.541572	0.2862	0.3021	0.94627	0.89642
100	0.2	92.14540	1.4	96.7	1.4	94.4148	0.980	0.990	2.269357	-2.269357	1.5930	1.6449	0.71227	0.68981
200	0.05	7.78350	3.3	9.04	3.3	8.4117	5.445	2.333	0.628233	-0.628233	0.3233	0.3571	0.97169	0.87963
200	0.1	44.47299	1.7	48.1	1.7	46.2868	1.445	1.202	1.813816	-1.813816	0.9387	0.9891	0.96612	0.91694
200	0.2	275.99867	3.1	318.1	3.1	297.0727	4.805	2.192	21.074037	-21.074037	10.7522	11.8184	0.97999	0.89158
500	0.05	52.94589	1.5	58.7	5.0	53.4232	2.064	1.437	0.477353	-5.303920	1.1045	3.0350	0.21610	0.87379
1000	0.05	204.98463	3	213.1	5.0	207.1346	6.618	2.572	2.150008	-5.972245	8.1369	11.9134	0.13211	0.25065

Table II: VAC 250F results

Frequency (kHz)	Magnetic Polarisation (T)	INRIM		NPL		Weighted Analysis			d_i		$u(d_i)$		E_n	
		Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty $k = 1$ (%)	Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty $k = 1$ (%)	$\bar{X}_{\text{weighted}}$ (W/kg)	St Dev.		INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL
							u^2 (%)	u (%)						
10	0.1	0.22584	1.0	0.2258	1.0	0.2258	0.500	0.707	0.000002	-0.000002	0.0028	0.0028	0.00028	0.00028
10	0.5	5.57658	1.8	6.06	1.8	5.8206	1.620	1.273	0.243981	-0.243981	0.1248	0.1319	0.97783	0.92468
20	0.1	0.64489	1.5	0.615	1.50	0.6297	1.125	1.061	-0.015164	0.015164	0.0118	0.0114	0.64501	0.66605
20	0.5	17.97911	1.5	16.81	1.5	17.3943	1.125	1.061	-0.584824	0.584824	0.3268	0.3124	0.89490	0.93592
50	0.1	2.86780	0.7	2.785	0.70	2.8265	0.245	0.495	-0.041273	0.041273	0.0245	0.0240	0.84337	0.85995
50	0.5	91.06248	1.4	96.8	1.4	93.9091	0.980	0.990	2.846629	-2.846629	1.5778	1.6429	0.90207	0.86634
100	0.1	9.51525	1.0	9.91	1.0	9.7107	0.500	0.707	0.195408	-0.195408	0.1173	0.1205	0.83265	0.81061
100	0.5	257.15919	3.5	302.3	3.5	279.7468	6.125	2.475	22.587628	-22.587628	11.3553	12.6454	0.99458	0.89312
200	0.1	34.61331	1.5	37.0	1.5	35.7917	1.125	1.061	1.178352	-1.178352	0.6432	0.6720	0.91603	0.87669
500	0.1	203.76220	1.5	215.7	1.5	209.7412	1.125	1.061	5.978962	-5.978962	3.7803	3.9268	0.79080	0.76131
1000	0.1	784.88504	1.5	783.6	1.5	784.2344	1.125	1.061	-0.650589	0.650589	14.4153	14.3993	0.02257	0.02259

Table III: VAC 500F results

Frequency (kHz)	Magnetic Polarisation (T)	INRIM		NPL		Weighted Analysis			d_i		$u(d_i)$		E_n	
		Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty $k = 1$ (%)	Power Loss (W/kg)	Measurement Uncertainty $k = 1$ (%)	$\bar{X}_{\text{weighted}}$ (W/kg)	St Dev.		INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL	INRIM	NPL
							u^2 (%)	u (%)						
10	0.1	0.10082	2.5	0.1133	2.5	0.1071	3.125	1.768	0.006252	-0.006252	0.0032	0.0034	0.99178	0.91751
10	0.5	2.67233	1	2.796	0.95	2.7372	0.474	0.689	0.064832	-0.058511	0.0327	0.0326	0.99120	0.89824
20	0.1	0.36193	3	0.413	3.0	0.3874	4.500	2.121	0.025420	-0.025420	0.0136	0.0149	0.93340	0.85522
20	0.5	9.33777	1	9.71	1.0	9.5241	0.500	0.707	0.186341	-0.186341	0.1151	0.1182	0.80927	0.78843
50	0.1	1.90754	3	2.19	3.0	2.0501	4.500	2.121	0.142564	-0.142564	0.0719	0.0789	0.99174	0.90395
50	0.5	46.13562	1.8	49.98	1.8	48.0589	1.620	1.273	1.923276	-1.923276	1.0314	1.0879	0.93236	0.88392
100	0.1	6.13733	4	7.36	4.0	6.7506	8.000	2.828	0.613238	-0.613238	0.3110	0.3510	0.98590	0.87350
100	0.5	154.36778	1.8	167.8	1.8	161.0928	1.620	1.273	6.725046	-6.725046	3.4532	3.6509	0.97373	0.92102
200	0.1	19.16569	5	23.8	5.0	21.5033	12.500	3.536	2.337646	-2.337646	1.2232	1.4139	0.95552	0.82669
200	0.5	532.17698	1.8	566.1	1.8	549.1207	1.620	1.273	16.943720	-16.943720	11.8579	12.3559	0.71445	0.68565
500	0.1	88.58134	5.5	113.2	5.5	100.8788	15.125	3.889	12.297508	-12.297508	6.2552	7.3579	0.98298	0.83567
1000	0.1	304.54726	5	363.9	5.0	334.2165	12.500	3.536	29.669228	-29.669228	19.2743	21.6947	0.76966	0.68379

7 Summary and conclusions

This technical report was produced by NPL, INRIM and UNOTT with the results of the high frequency loss comparison and an assessment of the measurement uncertainty found:

- In the ferrite the uncertainties were less than 1.5% for frequencies up to 200 kHz and less than 2.6% for 200 kHz and above.
- In the VAC 250F toroids the uncertainties were less than 1.5% for all frequencies except for 100 kHz, where the 0.5 T point had an uncertainty of 2.5%.
- In the VAC 500F toroids the uncertainties up to 1 MHz were between 1% and 4%.

A good practice guide for high frequency fluxmetric measurements using a wattmeter/hysteresisgraph circuit was prepared with a detailed description of the setup with explicative pictures of the circuit and measurement details.

Throughout the work two papers were published. The first paper focused on the high frequency behaviour of materials up to and above the MHz range. Reference:

“Magnetic Losses in Soft Ferrites” Samuel Dobák, Cinzia Beatrice, Vasiliki Tsakaloudi and Fausto Fiorillo *Magnetochemistry* **8**, (2022) 60. <https://doi.org/10.3390/magnetochemistry8060060>;

The second paper is devoted specifically to the topic of skin effects and is also relevant to D8-2. Reference:

“Skin effect and losses in soft magnetic sheets: from low inductions to magnetic saturation” O. de la Barrière, E. Ferrara, A. Magni, A. Sola, C. Ragusa, C. Appino, F. Fiorillo Published online to IEEE Transactions on Magnetism (May 2023) <https://hal.science/hal-04172888>;

8 References

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- [2] IEC 60404-10:2016: Magnetic Materials – Part 10: methods of measurement of magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet at medium frequencies.
- [3] IEC 60404-3:2022: Magnetic materials – Part 3: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of electrical steel strip and sheet by means of a single sheet tester.
- [4] IEC 60404-6:2018/AMD1:2021: Magnetic materials – Part 6: Methods of measurement of the magnetic properties of magnetically soft metallic and powder materials at frequencies in the range 20 Hz to 100 kHz by the use of ring specimens.
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